

A STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF WORK ENVIRONMENT ON TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE WITH RESPECT TO HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CHENNAI CITY

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Abstract

This article explains about the influences of work environment on teacher's performances in my school. This is a qualitative research and data was collected using a questionnaire. Around 50 responses from teachers of higher secondary schools were collected. School is a place where all the students learn their basics and shape their future. Therefore, providing quality education to school students plays a vital role in shaping up the economy. When discussing about quality education, the main facilitators who directly deal with are the teachers. They are the people who stand as a backbone in creating future doctors, engineers, entrepreneurs, etc. Therefore, evaluation of teacher's performance is very essential to boost up students' performance. Also, to elevate teacher's performance the schools should provide supportive environment. This study finds about the major influences that affect a teacher's performance with respect to work environment.

Key Factors: Teacher performance, Work environment, Shaping, Quality, Education, Facilitators.

INTRODUCTION

India had a crucial time during this pandemic due to COVID. During COVID, many companies faced numerous challenges to survive in the market. Not only as an industry but many schools have been shut down during had this pandemic and obviously many students suffered because of that unexpected situation. This article depicts about the major challenges that teachers faced because of their work environment during and post COVID.

In this article, we are going to see about, how the work environment influences the teacher's performances in school. During online classes, teachers handled the classes for students by using many applications. Muliatietal., (2022) conducted an survey on about the primary school teacher performances. They have used Spss software to analyse the data and they have collected 210 samples. Based on the analysi, they have concluded that the things were transformational Leadership, self-efficacy and competency affects teachers performances. Due to this pandemic, many companies have introduced many online platforms to take online classes for the students. These platforms helped teachers as well as the students to learn effectively. But obviously, there are positive as well as negative aspects while online classes were handled. Schools also faced many struggles during this pandemic. In order to overcome the challenges, they have implemented many methods such as conducting assessment test for the students, various day

activities to motivate and boost the student's performances, etc. The management also supported the staffs to take online classes effectively. But nothing will be as effective as face to face interaction. Because it helps both students and the teachers to know how they react or perform during the class. From this article, we are able to identify some of the factors that affect teacher's performance such as Aptitude, Attitude, Teaching methodology, Personal Characteristics, Classroom environment, Personality, student relationships, mental ability etc. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Suprpto et al. (2021) conducted a survey regarding the relationship between Organizational culture, motivation, and main leadership is the four independent variables that were examined in this study to determine their relationship. Here they have used purposive sampling. The data collected by the questionnaire. They used multiple linear regression Analysis for this study. They came to the conclusion that leadership style, motivational factors, and cultural organisation have no significant effect.

Ahmad et al. (2021) conducted a survey to find out the effect of work motivation on teachers job satisfaction and how they influenced their work motivation, job satisfaction on teacher performances. The case study used quantitative method and they have collected samples from 210 teachers with the help of questionnaire. Based on the analysis part they have concluded that organizational culture influences the organization which has a greater impact on teachers' performances. Leadership is not a significant effect on teacher's performances.

Shirzad et al. (2021) conducted a survey on public and private banks so they have determined the impact of strategic leadership on work performances, through the use of organisational commitment and job satisfaction they have used questionnaire method for data collection and they have collected from all the managers and the employees of public and private banks. They have used SPSS method for analyzing the data. According to the analysis, the strategic leadership behavior affects the organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Also, organizational commitment and job satisfaction affects work performances.

Tehseen & Hadi (2015) conducted a survey on the factors influencing Teachers performances and Retention. In this study, they explain about how quality teachers provide quality education in schools. The performances were seen by the management only through what they teach in class and how they get job satisfaction as well. Here, mainly they can talk about the extrinsic motivations like salary or wages, free accommodation, meals, any financial problems. But the major factors are working, administrative support, student behaviour, etc. This gives major effect on teacher's performances which should be reported to management.

Andrianetal. (2018) According to their research, transformational leadership and work motivation have an impact on teachers' effectiveness.. They have done a survey using quantitative method with correlational research type. They have collected data from 790

teachers of a particular institution. Using Sampling technique (Cluster Sampling) they have taken 193 samples. Questionnaire was given to the consultant teachers and they used multiple linear regression. From the research, they have concluded that transformational leadership and work motivation have significant effect on teacher's performances.

Haq et al. (2017) conducted a survey about teacher's performances. In this study they have prepared a questionnaire for collecting the samples and 166 samples were collected and they used PLS-SEM method to analyze the data. They discovered that emotional intelligence significantly affects how well employees accomplish their jobs. They have mostly concentrated on emotional self-awareness, self-confidence, success, developing others, and conflict management in their research. This has a big impact on how well teachers do their jobs.

Arifin (2015) have investigated the impact of organizational skill, motivation, and competence on the job performance and job satisfaction of teachers. In this study, they have conducted a survey and collected 346 samples using sampling technique. Questionnaire was given and data were analyzed by AMOS program. According to their study, job motivation significantly affects a teacher's job happiness. The effectiveness of teachers is also significantly influenced by competence and job satisfaction.

Baluyos et al (2019) conducted a research about the impact of job satisfaction on teachers' work performance. In this study, they have collected data from 313 school teachers and 104 head of the department. They have used Mean, standard deviation and Multiple Regression analysis method to analyze the data. From this, they concluded that teachers were highly satisfied by doing their jobs.

Anastasiou (2014) were done the research on job satisfaction, stress, and work performance on secondary education. From this study, they have collected 413 samples. They have found that teachers were more satisfied by doing their jobs and some inexperienced staff faces some stress while they do multitasking in their jobs. Environment plays a vital role for teacher's performance. Therefore, motivation is one of the key factors so that teachers would do their jobs in a proper way.

Ozgenel M., & Mert P., (2019) conducted a research on teacher's performances who can contribute towards the educational objectives. They have collected data by using survey method. 426 teachers have been filled the data and they used t-test, ANOVA, correlation, and regression. According to that, it's concluded that teacher's perception does not have any significant impact according to their gender and seniority. Here they mainly focused on the key factors such as school effectiveness, performances and teachers' performance. The results of this research clearly show that getting the feedbacks will give better idea on performance evaluation process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, we discuss about the effect of the workplace on teachers' performance. The method of analysis used in this study is Social Packages for the social services (SPSS). School teachers were the samples for this study and the sample size for this study was 50. Convenient sampling method is employed to collect data from school teachers. The below mentioned table depicts the frequency details of demographic profile of the respondents of this study.

Table 1: Frequency Analysis

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE		FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER	MALE	28	56
	FEMALE	22	44
AGE	<25 YEARS	14	28
	26-35 YEARS	23	46
	36-45 YEARS	12	24
	>45YEARS	1	2
QUALIFICATION	B. A, B.Ed.	3	6
	B. Sc, B.Ed.	6	12
	B. Com, B.Ed.	5	10
	M.A, M.Ed.	14	28
	M.Sc., M.Ed.	15	30
	M.Com, M.Ed.	7	14
EXPERIENCE	<10 YEARS	26	52
	11 -20YEARS	21	42
	21-30YEARS	2	4
	>30YEARS	1	2
DESIGNATION	HEAD	3	6
	ASSISTANT HEAD	3	6
	TEACHING STAFF	44	88

It is clear from summarized frequency table that Males make up the majority of respondents which is 56% followed by female which is 44%. From the analysis, the vast majority of respondents, are between 26 to 35 years of age followed by less than 25 years of age, 36 to 45 years of age and greater than 45 years of age. It is depicted from the above mentioned table that majority of respondents possess less than 10 years of experience followed by 11 to 20 of

experience, 21 - 30 years of experience and greater than 30 years of experience. The frequency table makes it evident that majority of the respondents are teaching staffs followed by heads and assistant heads who are headmasters, headmistress, assistant headmasters and assistant headmistress. Table 2 demonstrates about the challenges faced by teachers during online classes through mean analysis.

Table 2: Challenges faced by teachers during online classes

S. No	Challenges	Mean	Rank
1	Lack of fair assessments	3.64	5
2	Lack of interactions from student	3.92	4
3	Frequent absenteeism	3.92	3
4	Network issues	4.00	2
5	Non-availability of mobile phones	4.22	1

From the above analysis, we can conclude that majority of the teachers feel that non availability of mobile phones were the most challenging factors during their online classes followed by other factors like network issues, frequent absenteeism from students' side, lack of interactions from students and assessment tests. Table 3 demonstrates about the reward programs for teachers during online classes through mean analysis.

Table 3: Reward Programmes for teachers during online classes

S. No	Reward Programmes	Mean	Rank
1	The school provides intrinsic and extrinsic reward programme	3.96	2
2	Teachers are promoted on their qualifications and performances appraisal through intrinsic rewards	4.00	1

From the above analysis, about reward program employed in the schools for teachers during online classes, we can conclude that the teachers feel that they were promoted based on their qualifications and performance appraisal. As it possess highest mean value followed by the variable intrinsic and extrinsic reward programme. Therefore, it is evident that during online classes also teachers were promoted based on their qualification and performance appraisal played a ket role in teachers' promotion. Table 4 demonstrates about the facilities provided by schools to teachers for smooth conduction of online classes through mean analysis.

Table 4: Facilities provided by schools to teachers during online classes

S. No	Facilities	Mean	Rank
1	The school has adequate infrastructure to support teachers performances	3.78	4
2	My school provides proper tools and technology for performing tasks	3.84	3
3	My school have enough facilities to take online classes in schools	4.02	2
4	My school provided specific application for conducting online assessments	4.16	1

From the above analysis, it is evident that majority of the schools have provided specific applications for conducting online assessments. Also it gives additional information that through this enabled platforms it is very easy for teachers to give assignments, home works after class, assessments, etc. his variable possess highest mean value followed by schools have enough facilities to take online classes in schools, schools provided tools and technology for performing tasks and schools provide adequate support for teachers/ performances. Table 5 demonstrates about the leadership style employed by schools for effective performance of teachers during online classes through mean analysis.

Table 5: Leadership Style employed by schools for effective teacher's performance during online classes

S. No	Leadership Style	Mean	Rank
1	The school administration adopts both consultative and participative leadership style	3.76	4
2	Subordinates can say their views and get the constant feedbacks from the superior	3.92	3
3	Employees were involved frequently in decision making through zoom platform	3.96	2
4	Subordinates were involved in planning activities of the school	4.00	1

From the above analysis, it is evident that majority of the schools involve teachers in their planning processes. This is because the management strongly believes that teachers are the facilitators so if they are coming with the plan it will be more feasible in the real time. The subordinates were involved in planning activities if the school variable possess highest mean value followed by other variables like employees were involved in decision making through zoom platform, Subordinates can say their views and get the constant feedbacks from the superior and The school administration adopts both consultative and participative leadership style.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of analysis, it is evident that offline classes are more effective than online classes but still majority of the schools have done a great job during COVID times in providing quality education to students. If the teachers can do their job really well, then the management should give performance appraisal for the teachers in order to boost their performances and do their job effectively. Nowadays, the practice has been changed due to COVID, that online classes also can be conducted in an effective manner. But schools should focus on the students who are failing in their assessment tests, students who are frequently absent, etc. Schools should employ alternative ideas to manage these type of situations. Here the leadership style used by the school administration was both consultative and participative which is very much appreciable. The management should support their teachers to performance well by providing adequate facilities and supportive work environment. This will not only provide quality education to students but also help in shaping their future and getting good image from parents. This will enhance more referrals to the schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research, we conclude that majority of the teachers performance are influenced strongly by the work environment. The concept is that there are many challenges that are faced by the teachers during online classes and management also played a major role in supporting the teachers effectively. According to the results, we suggest that that Non availability of mobile phones is a major factor to attend online classes and also lack of interactions between the teacher and the student. This type of poor interaction leads to system failure. Offline classes are better than online classes in which teachers can get attention and they can do better for their students' performance. Although teachers struggle hard, schools should make sure that teachers are provided with appropriate work environment and adequate facilities to facilitate smooth functioning of classes.

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